

Tracheobronchopathia osteochondroplastica: Are We Overlooking?

Tracheobronchopathia osteochondroplastica: Gözden Kaçırıyor muyuz?

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Dear editor,

A 60-year-old man was admitted to our clinic with complaints of dry cough and recurrent upper and lower respiratory tract infections for about three years. Respiratory system examination, chest radiography, routine blood tests and pulmonary function tests were normal. The patient had three previous thoracic computed tomography (CT) scans, but only one CT report mentioned calcified nodules causing minimal irregularity in the tracheal wall. The CT scan of the thorax showed calcified nodules and millimetric formations causing minimal irregularity in the tracheal wall (**Figure 1a**). Bronchoscopy revealed irregular, multiple white nodules on the anterior and lateral walls of the trachea extending to the carina. The posterior wall of the trachea was also preserved (**Figure 1b**). Histopathological examination of the tissue samples revealed bone tissue formation,

sup mucosal ossification and cartilage structure under the airway epithelium (**Figure 1c**). Nonspecific treatment was planned and the patient is still being followed up without complications.

Tracheobronchopathia osteochondroplastica (TO) is a rare, benign, usually asymptomatic disease characterised by multiple, slowly growing, sup mucosal bone and cartilage nodules extending into the lumen of the tracheobronchial tree (1). It usually occurs in the 4th and 5th decades and there is no gender difference (2). Etiological and pathological mechanisms contributing to the formation of TO are not fully understood. Chronic infections, irritants, metabolic disorders and genetic predisposition are blamed in the etiology (3). Patients with TO may be asymptomatic or may present with severe symptoms and complications including cough, dyspnoea, recurrent lung

Figure 1. Thorax CT, bronchoscopy and histopathological findings of the case. a: Thorax CT shows calcification nodules, milimetric formations causing minimal irregularity in the trachea wall. b: Bronchoscopy shows numerous white irregular nodules extending from the anterior and lateral walls of the trachea. c: Bone tissue is seen under the epithelium of the respiratory tract showing squamous metaplasia. HE staining x 20 magnification.

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infections and haemoptysis. In asymptomatic individuals, TO may be detected incidentally on autopsy, routine bronchoscopy and thoracic CT (4). Chest radiography is usually normal, but irregularities, tracheal stenosis or lobar atelectasis may be observed in some patients. Thoracic CT shows diffuse calcified nodules protruding from the anterolateral tracheal lumen and preservation of the posterior wall of the trachea. On bronchoscopy, diffuse submucosal nodules of 1-10 mm protruding into the tracheal lumen involving the distal 2/3 of the trachea and preservation of the posterior wall of the trachea are typical (2). In our case, ossific nodules extending from the supraglottic region to the carina and main bronchial inlet were present. Characteristic histopathological findings include cartilage and ossification, calcification and mucosal squamous metaplasia in the tracheal submucosa. Biopsy may be helpful in the differential diagnosis of diseases such as amyloidosis, mucoepidermoid carcinoma, papillomatosis, sarcoidosis, although it is not necessary due to typical bronchoscopy appearances. The prognosis of patients with TO is generally good, treatment depends on symptoms and is nonspecific (1,5). In our patient, the biopsy result was reported as bone tissue under the respiratory tract epithelium showing squamous metaplasia.

We were able to recognise this case of TO with bronchoscopy, but in retrospect, we aimed to show that an earlier diagnosis can be made with Thorax CT. Thorax CT stands out as a noninvasive diagnostic tool in the diagnosis and differential diagnosis of TO. We believe that TO should be included in the differential diagnosis of clinicians and radiologists and that Thorax CT can guide the clinician to early bronchoscopy and diagnosis.

Keywords: Bronchoscopy, chronic cough, endotracheal lesions, nodular trachea

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